

Implementation of Safety Behavior on Occupational Safety and Health in the Bonded and Logistic Services Division of Pt. Gmf Aeroasia Tbk

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Abstract:- Safe behavior (safety behavior) is an attitude that does not lead to the formation of accidents or incidents, where a person maintains the safety of his work area by following safety procedures and consuming personal protective equipment. This study aims to find out how the condition of implementing safety behavior on occupational health and safety in the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk, To find out what factors violate the implementation of safety behavior that cause work accidents related to occupational safety and health in the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk, To find out what obstacles are experienced in implementing safety behavior towards occupational safety and health in the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk, To create and analyze how the correct safety behavior implementation concept model for occupational safety and health in the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk. The results of this study are in the form of answers to existing problem formulations such as regarding the condition of implementing safety behavior on occupational health and safety, where at PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk especially the Bonded and Logistic Services divisions are guided by a guideline rule, the rule is named "HSE Manual", factors of violation of safety behavior such as working not in accordance with guidelines/procedures, lack of awareness and not focusing on work, not checking tools or equipment according to guidelines causes work accidents, obstacles in implementing safety behavior such as working in a hurry due to pursuing TAT which must be achieved immediately, do not understand safety behavior guidelines properly, work deadlines so employees often forget safety and safety regulations as well as Turnover and working time deadlines must be completed immediately and in the form of a new strategy/concept from the guidelines regarding safety

behavior and occupational health and safety in the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk.

Keywords:- Safety Behavior, Occupational health and safety, Bonded and Logistic Services Division PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Resources is the driving force behind a company. Human resources control work equipment as well as all forms of work related to the description of each work item. With this important responsibility, the company has a duty to carry out maintenance and protection for employees. Employee maintenance and protection includes aspects of occupational safety and health, both related to the attitude of the workforce or the work area and equipment.

Safety behavior itself is a systematic application of psychological research on human behavior in workplace safety issues. Safety behavior emphasizes aspects of human behavior towards accidents in the workplace. Safety behavior began to appear in 1980 and began to be implemented in the early 1990s.

Previous research conducted by Dieqa Raras Anggary (2012) concluded that the implementation of good safety behavior will affect the health and safety of employees, where applying the correct safety behavior can be used to assess safe behavior and reduce work accidents as well as the perceived benefits of implementing safety behavior is the creation of a work culture and work safety that leads to safe behavior. In addition, the results of research conducted by Sialagan (2008) at PT. EGS Indonesia, it was concluded that where there is a significant relationship between factors of knowledge, motivation, and perceptions of worker safety behavior.

Table 1: Development of the Number of K3 Interference Cases in the Logistics and Bonded Service Division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk throughout 2020 to 2022

Year	Number of Cases	Development	Case Type
		(%)	
2020	1	12%	Occupational injury
2021	3	37%	Occupational injury, Chemical Hazard
2022	4	50%	Occupational injury, Heavy equipment hazard, Danger of parts/goods

Source: Sag Bonded and Logistic Services Division of Work Accidents Pt. Gmf Aeroasia Tbk 2020-2022

In general, from Table 1 it can be concluded that the categorization of the types of K3 problems in the logistics and bonded service divisions of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk is included in the 4, namely work-related injuries, work-related illnesses, OHS hazards due to chemicals, heavy equipment/parts/objects. The growth in the number of problems itself is experiencing fluctuations, where the number of problems that occur the most in 2022 is 6 = 3 problems, or an increase compared to the number of problems in 2021.

- There is an implementation of safety behavior that is wrong and not good by employees of the logistics and Bonded Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk in terms of completing the work undertaken.

- Awareness of employees that needs to be increased in implementing safety behavior properly.
- SOP regarding the implementation of existing safety behavior has not been fully understood and implemented properly in the work of employees.
- The problem of implementing safety behavior that is not correct affects the number of work accidents that occur in the logistics and Bonded Services divisions of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk.

Therefore, the researcher determined the research title for the research thesis, namely "Implementation of safety behavior on occupational health and safety in the Logistics and Bonded Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk.

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From the problems faced by the Logistics and Bonded Services Division at PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk, the authors can identify and formulate the problems encountered and the issues to be raised based on the background previously described as follows:

- What are the conditions of safety behavior towards occupational safety and health in the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk?
- What are the factors of implementing safety behavior that affect occupational safety and health in the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk?
- What obstacles are experienced in implementing safety behavior towards occupational safety and health in the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk?
- What is the correct concept of implementing safety behavior for occupational safety and health in the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMFAeroasia Tbk?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Occupational Health and Safety

Philosophically, occupational health and safety are defined as ideas and efforts to maintain the perfection of employees and humans, both physically and mentally, work and culture towards a just, prosperous and prosperous society. Although scientifically occupational safety and

health is defined as science and its application to prevent work accidents, fires, environmental pollution, diseases, etc. (Triyono, 2014).

Meanwhile, the definition of K3 according to the Occupational Safety Health Administration (OSHA) is the application of knowledge in studying human and property safety risks both in industry and not. Occupational health and safety is a multidisciplinary science consisting of physics, chemistry, biology and behavioral science with applications in manufacturing, transportation, handling of hazardous materials (Sujoso, 2012).

B. Occupational Safety and Health (K3) Objectives

Occupational health and safety aims to guarantee the perfection or physical and spiritual health of employees and their work and culture. The main goal in organizing K3 based on Law no. 1/1970 on occupational safety, i.e. missed.

- Protect and ensure the safety of every employee and others in the workplace.
- Ensuring that every source of production can be used safely and efficiently.
- Improving national welfare and productivity.

C. Benefits of Occupational Safety and Health (K3)

Important benefits in implementing K3, namely (Koreilis & Gunawan, 2018):

- Employee protection, the core objective of implementing K3 is to be able to provide protection to the workforce.
- Demonstrates Compliance with Rules and Laws. Companies that comply with laws and regulations and show goodwill to carry on business normally without hindering work
- Cost reduction: Implementation of OSH avoids accidents, damage and chain of custody, minimizes organizational costs such as insurance premiums.
- Establish an effective management system.

- All ongoing activities and activities are regulated, directed and carried out in an orderly corridor through documented procedures.
- Increase customer trust and satisfaction. G. Perceptions of the spread of OSH improve the image of the organization related to its performance, which naturally affects the increase in customer trust.

D. Work Accident Classification

According to (Kristiawan and Abdullah, 2018), the classification of work accidents in Indonesia is divided into:

- *Based on severity:*
 - Death due to a work accident if the victim dies within 24 hours of the work accident
 - Serious injury if the accident victim is unable to work for more than 3 weeks.
 - Minor personal injury if victim is unable to work within 3 weeks
- *Classification by Type of Accident:*
 - Dropped, crushed or dropped by objects or work objects.
 - Tripping over an object or object, bumping into an object, sandwiched between two objects.
 - Exposure to hot objects or high temperatures.
 - Got electrocuted.
 - Exposure to hazardous materials or radiation.
- *Classification by type of accident:*
 - Dropped, hit, or dropped by an object or workpiece.
 - Tripping over an object or object, hitting an object, or being caught between two objects.
 - Contact with hot or hot objects.
 - Electrocuted to death.
 - Exposure to hazardous substances or radiation.
- *Classification based on the type of wound or injury:*
 - Fracture
 - a sprain or sprain
 - muscle pain and cramps
 - Concussion and other internal injuries
 - amputation and extraction (removal of organs or removal to damage the cell nucleus)
 - Scratches and other exterior stains
 - Bruises and tears
 - Burns
 - Addicted
 - apnea or shortness of breath
 - The effect of exposure to electric current
 - Effects of radiation exposure
 - Scars on many parts of the body or elsewhere

E. Factors Causing Work Accidents

Basically, the causes of work accidents can be influenced by two factors (Utari, 2020):

- *Situations of Uncertainty*
Accidents occur due to a dangerous work environment because personal protective equipment does not comply with procedures. For example the personal protective equipment

(PPE) provided does not meet standards, so work accidents can occur which can have a negative impact. For example, the helmets worn by employees must be made of a material that can withstand the impact of hard objects. The work environment also plays an important role. Offices that do not meet occupational health and safety standards and requirements can result in decreased productivity and productivity. In addition, the workers themselves can be negatively affected. An example is the lack of proper ventilation, which prevents air exchange in the work area and deprives workers of oxygen.

➤ *Dangerous Behavior*

When an accident occurs due to unsafe acts or following actions

- Performing work that is different from the skills and abilities that should be done due to lack of knowledge and skills.
- Work must master the field of work. This is to avoid mistakes and accidents in the future. For example, a mechanic must be familiar with all kinds of machine parts, such as tools, and understand their functions. Do not press in the wrong way as it may cause industrial accidents.
- If the work process is not carried out properly, workers who do not carry out the work process properly can cause losses to the company where they work, especially for the workers themselves.
- Unsafe attitudes and behavior, such as working while joking and joking is a behavior that must be eliminated because it can result in very fatal incidents that cause not only material losses, but also non-material losses. Various causal factors are simultaneously present in a workplace, which can cause work accidents. From several research results, experts state that a work accident cannot happen by itself, but occurs by one or several factors that cause accidents at once in an incident.

Meanwhile, the following are several factors that cause work accidents, namely (Wijayanti, 2017):

- **Technical Factors:** Is one aspect that can cause a potential hazard originating from the work tools used or from the work itself.
- **Environmental factor:** Is one aspect that can pose a potential hazard that originates from the environment, which originates from the production process such as the raw materials used, both products and final results. This environmental factor is commonly referred to as an unsafe condition. Unsafe condition is an unsafe condition of machinery, equipment, aircraft, materials, work environment, work processes, nature of work and work systems.
- **Human Factors:** It is a potential hazard if the person doing the work is not in good health condition, both physically and psychologically so that it can be dangerous for himself or others which can cause an accident. The human factor is also referred to as unsafe action (Unsafe Action).

F. Impact Due to Work Accidents

- Occupational accidents can cause 5 different types of damage, namely:
- Offenses, organizational chaos, complaints and sorrow, abandonment and deprivation and death. According to Heinrich, a list of possible accidental damages is as follows (Wahyudi, 2018):
- Losses due to the absence of injured workers
- Lost time for other employees who stop working out of curiosity, compassion or helping injured employees
- Losses experienced by workers, supervisors or other supervisors due to lost time to help injured workers find out the causes of accidents, manage the production process at the workplace of injured workers, continue other workers by selecting and training or recruiting new workers.
- Lost time of rescue workers and hospital staff
- Damage caused by damage to machinery, equipment or other equipment or contamination of raw materials.
- Accidental losses due to production stoppages, failure to fulfill orders on time, loss of prizes, payment of fines or other similar consequences
- Losses arising from the introduction of an employee welfare system,
- Losses if previously injured workers return to work and continue to be paid full wages even though they are producing (perhaps not fully paid) at half their normal capacity.
- Losses from lost opportunities for productivity gains injured workers and the consequences of useless machines.
- Losses due to excitement or reduced morale due to the accident.
- Common cost losses (overhead costs) for injured employees.

G. Work Accident Prevention

There are 5 work accident prevention measures that can be used by an organization, namely (Muliawan et al, 2018):

- *Identification of Hazards and Environmental Problems*
Whenever a project is started or a new activity is started, the safety manager must identify the potential hazards and environmental issues that affect the people involved in the project activity and their environment.
- *Safety instructions*
Safety briefing is education for all new employees who come to the project area and for employees who do the same job. There is a high risk. This safety briefing is intended for contractor and subcontractor employees.
- *HSE inspection*
The owner, MK, PM/SM and project HSE team conduct HSE audits once a week to check and ensure that contractors, subcontractors and foremen carry out HSE consistently. The Safety Officer should take into account any HSE non-conformances identified during the inspection and pass the report on to the party who has to follow up.

➤ *Security Patrol*

Safety Patrol is a regular patrol used by TeamSafety to check the condition/condition of the project environment and check all construction activities as well as preventive measures to avoid accidents and pollution.

➤ *Security Discussion*

Safety talk is intended for employees and employees in the workplace. The essence of this safety talk guides the implementation of HSE and aims so that the workforce can work safely.

➤ *Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)*

Personal protective equipment consists of several parts, namely:

- Helmet
- Safety shoes
- Seatbelt
- Gloves
- Safety glasses
- Face mask
- Earplugs and earplugs
- Bring a pack

H. Safety Behaviour

Safe behavior/safety behavior (Rusdijati, Sugiarto et al.: 2017) is conduct that does not lead to an accident or dangerous situation. The difference between safe behavior and work safety behavior is that safe behavior only focuses on safety while OSH behavior does not only focus on safety but also on health.

Below are types to use safely, including:

- Work will be carried out after approval.
- Successfully warned of danger.
- Successfully secure the work area and people around it
- Work at a certain speed.
- Keep safety devices operational.
- Do not remove the health protection device.
- Use proper tools.
- Wear appropriate PPE.
- Fill the tool or machine according to the applicable regulations. Safe behavior/safety behavior (Rusdijati, Sugiarto et al.: 2017) is behavior that does not cause accidents or dangerous situations. The difference between safe behavior and work safety behavior is that safe behavior only focuses on safety while OSH behavior does not only focus on safety but also on health.

I. Components of Safety Behavior

Safety behavior consists of two parts, namely compliance with safety requirements and participation in safety. In contrast, safety regulations refer to the primary responsibility of humans to ensure the maintenance of a safe work environment. This behavior is reflected in the observation of normal work processes and the use of personal protective equipment.

Safety participation, on the other hand, is a better understanding of employees' desire to work actively to improve job safety. This goal is seen in tasks related to employee safety, assisting colleagues in safety matters and safety activities.

J. Factors influencing safety behavior

Safety behavior is influenced by external and internal factors. Suizer (Novianto, 2017) explains four internal types that affect safety behavior, including:

➤ Perception

Workforce checks to understand threats in the work environment. If an employee has a negative sense of security, they behave dangerously. Conversely: If an employee has a good understanding of safety, he or she will behave safely. Employees' ability to recognize hazards in the workplace is influenced by their sensory abilities, alertness, and perceptions.

➤ Cognitive

This factor is related to the knowledge and understanding of the workforce about safety hazards and risks in the work environment. When the workforce lacks knowledge and understanding, it leads to poor safety behavior. At this point, it all depends on the education, experience, memory and mental abilities of the individual.

➤ Decision making

Safety behavior is invisible when employees are unable to make important and correct decisions. The decision is to avoid accidents when you know the danger you are in. It relies on education, experience, attitude, motivation, personality and willingness to take risks.

➤ Ability

Safety behavior can arise when a worker is able to behave safely or avoid danger. This phase is influenced by physical abilities. Then safety behavior is influenced by external factors, namely the role of supervisors in supporting employee safety behavior. This support is a way of maintaining and prioritizing safety to clarify the expected safety behavior in different working conditions. Excellent support for employees in the form of psychosocial support. With the help of this social support, employees develop a sense of responsibility and a desire to work towards achieving company goals. This condition of providing psychosocial support helps employees feel organizational support and a high safety climate. Through this social sharing mechanism, employees are encouraged to engage in safety behavior. Management support is critical because failure to improve safety behavior is usually due to a lack of management support and commitment. Managers' commitment to safety is usually demonstrated by rewarding employees who behave safely by providing tools and assistance for immediate action, providing feedback, and taking safe behavior initiatives whenever possible.

K. Implementation

Definition of Implementation According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI), implementation means carrying out or carrying out. (Wahyudi: 2015) argues that implementation is an extraordinary thing that happens or the

application of something that produces a result. According to Muljad: (2015), implementation initiates initiatives to achieve the goals set out in the resolution. The goal of this activity is to convert the decision into a more feasible model and to achieve major or minor changes in a pre-decided manner.

Implementation steps include:

- Program development which includes annual, semiannual or quarterly, monthly, weekly and daily programs. In addition, there are also orientation and counseling programs or rehabilitation programs.
- Implementation of learning. Learning is essentially an interaction between students and their environment. So there is a change in behavior for the better.
- Evaluation, the process carried out during the curriculum implementation process quarterly or semester by semester, and the final formative or summative assessment, including a thorough assessment to evaluate the implementation of the curriculum as a whole.

L. Implementation Stages

According to (Agustino: 2012) there are several factors that influence the success of an implementation, including:

➤ Communication Factor

Communication is defined as the process of delivering information to the communicant communicator. Policy communication means the process of conveying policy information from public policy makers that needs to be conveyed to policy actors so that policy actors can know, understand what is the content, goals, directions, target groups of policies so that policy actors can properly prepare what must be prepared and do to carry out public policy so that the goals and objectives of the policy can be achieved as expected.

➤ Resources

Resource factors have an important role in implementing resource policies including human resources, budget resources, equipment resources, and information and authority resources. The resource indicator consists of several elements, namely: staff, information, facilities and authority.

➤ Disposition

Disposition is the will, desire and tendency of policy actors to implement policies seriously so that what is the goal of the policy can be realized.

➤ Bureaucratic Structure

The success of implementation is a bureaucratic structure. Even if the resources are available to implement the policy or the implementers of the policy know what needs to be done and are willing to implement the policy, it is very likely that the policy cannot be implemented or enforced due to weaknesses in the bureaucratic structure. Such complex guidelines require the cooperation of many people. When the bureaucratic structure is not conducive to available policies, it causes resource inefficiencies and makes policy implementation difficult. As an

implementation of bureaucratic politics, you must be able to support it.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

In compiling the paper, the researcher provides a post-positivism paradigm. The positivist paradigm is a paradigm that was first propagated by scholars and then criticized by their followers, giving rise to a new view called postpositivism. This paradigm is also referred to as the scientific method of qualitative research. Where, this paradigm views that causes (causative factors) are very likely to determine the final result or outcome. The considerations and reasons for using the post-positivist paradigm are as follows:

- The problem and purpose of this research was conducted to see social phenomena that occur as systematic symptoms
- To obtain data in the study, the researcher conducted direct observations and interviews with informants within the framework of the scientific process as required by the post-positivism paradigm, namely that there is a relationship between the researcher and the research subject, so that the researcher is able to understand and translate how social actors reproduce the social world that the researcher observes.
- In fact, the effectiveness of the concept of talent management on the sustainability of a business in a company is related to the progress of a company.
- In analyzing the data, from the beginning, the researcher collected various data and information as well as other sources of knowledge, the researcher tried to build an induction thinking framework, which then compared with the theory of occupational health and safety and other theories used in this study.
- For this reason, the problems found will be studied by researchers with a post-positivism paradigm so that they can identify the causal obstacles that affect the final outcome of the implementation of safety behavior on occupational health and safety in the logistics and bonded services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk.

A. Research Design/Strategy

Conceptually, the definition of research design is a design regarding the entire process required in planning and conducting research (Silaen, 2018). Furthermore, there are several types of research designs or strategies, but in this study, the researcher used a case study research design which emphasizes the exploration of a specific case as a research problem which is then developed and used as the focus of investigation.

B. Concept definition

The conceptual definition is the meaning of the concept used, making it easier for researchers to operate the concept in the field. Based on this understanding, the conceptual definition used in this study is:

➤ Occupational health and safety

According to Elphiana (2017), the definition of occupational health and safety is showing conditions that are safe or safe from suffering, damage or loss in the workplace. Occupational safety and health is important and must receive serious attention. Indonesia also has serious attention to occupational safety and health Ensuring occupational safety and health can foster morale among employees. Based on the law, employees have the right to occupational health and safety in their implementation.

➤ Safety Behaviour

According to (Rusdijati, Sugiarto et al.: 2017). The definition of safety behavior is behavior that does not cause an accident or incident. The difference between safe behavior and occupational safety and health behavior is that safe behavior only focuses on safety, while K3 behavior does not only focus on safety but also on health.

➤ Implementation

According to (Mulyadi: 2015). The definition of implementation is something that triggers action to achieve the goals that have been set in a decision. This action seeks to transform these decisions into a more operational pattern and seeks to achieve big or small changes as previously decided.

C. Social Situation

This research was conducted in the Material Department Unit Logistics and Bonded Services PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk. The researcher is an internal employee of the Logistics and Bonded Services Unit of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk , so that researchers know the detailed picture related to the implementation of safety behavior on occupational health and safety in the Logistics and Bonded Services division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. General Description of the Research Object

PT Garuda Maintenance Facility (GMF Aeroasia) Tbk is a company headquartered at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, Tangerang, Banten and is a company engaged in the Maintenance, Repair and Overhaul (MRO) sector with various international recognitions and certifications from the Directorate of Airworthiness and Aircraft Operation (DKPPU), Federal Aviation and Administration (FAA), and European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA). The journey of PT Garuda Maintenance Facility Aero Asia Tbk (“the Company” or “GMF”) started with the formation of the Garuda Indonesia Technical Directorate in 1949.

The code hierarchy and details in Nvivo are known as Codebooks.

Fig. 1. Mind Map of PT GMF Aeroasia K3 safety behavior conditions, Bonded and Logistic Services division

The following is a mind map of PT GMF Aeroasia's OHS safety behavior condition, Bonded and Logistic Services division, which consists of 4 themes, namely guidelines, work accidents, benefits, understanding and discipline. Which will later answer the formulation of the

problem in this study regarding the condition of safety behavior, factors, obstacles and input suggestions for the Bonded and Logistic Services division of PT. GMF Aeonesia Tbk. The details of the theme will be explained in the project map below.

Fig. 2: Rules Guidelines

On the theme of the rule guidelines regarding the implementation of safety behavior on occupational health and safety, the results of data analysis can be reviewed through three aspects, namely safety behavior guidelines,

access to safety behavior guidelines, and socialization of safety behavior carried out. The following is an explanation of these points:

Fig. 3: Analysis of regulatory guidelines related to K3 safety behavior at PT GMF Aeroasia

From the results of the analysis above regarding the regulatory guidelines related to K3 safety behavior at PT GMF aeroasia the regulatory guidelines follow the HSE management manual as stated by the informants, but according to one informant who is a logistics controller, the regulatory guidelines can also be in the form of GADL.

In addition, it was concluded that the HSE management manual contains HSE work scope, safety behavior, company profile, use of PPE, HSE Policy, hazard identification management, hydras hazard. Meanwhile, safety culture also includes a workspace as conveyed by all informants whose positions are (senior bonded zone analyst, unserviceable store manager, seniormanager and logistics controller).

Fig. 4: Dissemination of K3 Safety Behavior Guidelines

Furthermore regarding the socialization of K3 safety behavior rules guidelines, the results of data analysis can be concluded from the results of interviews, the informant who has a position as a logistics controller stated that the socialization was carried out routinely every month in each division and their respective superiors to the subordinates,

while 3 other informants said the socialization was carried out via administrative email to all employees of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk includes the Bonded and Logistic Services divisions regarding guidelines for safety behavior rules by the agency in charge of Occupational Health and Safety / HSE.

Fig. 5: Work Accident Analysis

On the theme of work accidents above, the results of the data analysis consist of several aspects including factors that cause work accidents, work accidents that have occurred

in the last 3 years, work accidents that have been experienced, chronology of work accidents, and obstacles in implementing safety behavior that cause work accidents.

Fig. 6: Work Accident Factors

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safety culture also includes a workspace as conveyed by all informants whose positions are (senior bonded zone analyst, unserviceable store manager, seniormanager and logistics controller).

Fig. 7: Barriers Experienced by Employees

Obstacles in implementing safety behavior itself according to the results of data analysis of interviews with informants, the obstacles experienced by employees in

implementing safety behavior correctly in accordance with the guidelines consist of several obstacles.

Fig. 8: Accident Experience Employee Responses

The responses from the informants when the researchers asked whether the informants had experienced a work accident or not and if so, what was the chronology of a work accident that could have happened to them. Informants

who have positions as Senior Manager, Senior Bonded Zone Analyst, Bonded Compliance Manager, Logistic Controller answered that they had never experienced a work accident.

Fig. 9: Accident Cases in the Last 3 Years

The results of data analysis regarding work accident cases that have occurred in the last 3 years, the conclusion from the answers of the informants, work accidents are divided into 2, namely minor and major work accidents. However, what is being investigated is work accidents that are major in nature, such as employees who are squeezed

while working, are caught when closing a sliding door; Run over by a forklift, employee's hand caught in the door. Meanwhile, the number of work-related accident cases at PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk over the past 3 years there have been 30 cases and for the Bonded and Logistic Services divisions there have been 2 cases.

Fig. 10: Understanding and Discipline

From the results of interviews with informants, understanding and discipline consisted of aspects including the discipline of implementing safety behavior, aspects of

understanding safety behavior guidelines, and aspects of attitude and concern for safety behavior.

Fig. 11: Aspects of Attitude and Concern

In the aspect of attitude and concern as well as discipline towards safety behavior, it can be shown through the responses from the informants, namely attitudes, care and concern are good, understand and care about occupational health and safety. However, in contrast to other informants, the informant who has the position of HSE Senior Manager and Bonded Compliance Manager has a lack of attitude, discipline and concern for the importance of

safety behavior. Meanwhile, from the disciplinary aspect of implementing safety behavior, there are many employees who have not worked according to safety guidelines, rediscipline of implementing guidelines can still be improved, employees are disciplined in implementing safety guidelines, and there are employees who have not implemented safety guidelines.

Fig. 12: Guidelines for Safety Behavior

The results of the interview data analysis regarding the understanding of safety behavior guidelines led to conclusions, as there are employees who understand the guidelines for safety behavior rules but do not care enough

so they do not apply safety behavior guidelines at work and colleagues who are influenced by other people who do not behave according to safety guidelines, there are also those who really understand manual HSE guidelines starting

operating work tools, self-protection equipment, safety behavior, danger symbols and have read and studied the HSE manual and finally from the answers of the informants

gave the answer that there are co-workers who already know about the HSE manual but do not delve further.

Fig. 13: Benefits of Safety Behavior

On the theme of the benefits of safety behavior, several things can be studied and discussed, namely the

effectiveness of safety behavior, the benefits of implementing safety behavior; and suggestions and input.

Fig. 14: Effectiveness of Safety Behavior and Benefits of Implementing Safety Behavior

The results of the analysis of interview data regarding the effectiveness of safety behavior and the benefits of implementing safety behavior in accordance with the guidelines, the conclusions obtained include that manual

HSE is effective in reducing the number of work accidents, if there is an accident incident, manual HSE is always reviewed for improvement.

Fig. 15: Suggestions and Feedback

The results of data analysis from the results of interviews with informants are regarding suggestions and input on the HSE Manual safety behavior rule guidelines. The results of suggestions and input obtained are:

- Can hold a safety behavior implementation competition to encourage employee enthusiasm for safety behavior,
- Unexpected visits by management can be made to control K3 and safety behavior to units in one of which are the Bonded and Material Services divisions
- Carry out more stringent supervision of safety behavior;
- HSE can be made fun, such as holding competitions related to safety
- Improvement HSE manual from external audit so that it is more complete
- More intensive sharing or morning and evening briefings conducted by managers to subordinates
- More aggressively implementing and declaring a safety work culture that complies with the guidelines for employees
- Make routine medical check up activities for employees
- Have a place for employees to report to the authorized unit if they see co-workers who do not comply with the guidelines
- Adding points to form BBS (behavior best safety) in each agency in the HSE manual

- Added safety behavior assessment for other people in the HSE manual
- Addition of symbols or hazard signs or road lanes for heavy equipment
- Routinely reviewing safety guidelines regarding regulatory policies to program items
- More even dissemination of K3 guidelines to all employees
- Make rules related to punishment for employees who do not implement safety according to guidelines.

B. Hierarki chart:

A hierarchy chart is a diagram that can show rectangular data hierarchies of various sizes and can also see a hierarchy chart in round form. The various sizes are determined by showing the number, for example the number of coding on nodes or the number of references from coding entered according to the contents of the article found by the researcher. The chart hierarchy best scales according to the available space so that the dimensions of the rectangles must be considered in relation to one another, not in absolute numbers. The largest area is shown on the top left of the graph, while the smallest area is shown on the bottom right of the graph. the use of chart hierarchies because they want to see the dominance of coding.

Fig. 16: Factors Causing Work Accidents

Cluster analysis is an exploratory methodology used to visualize project design by grouping sources or nodes with similar terms, similar attribute values, or similar to nodes. Analysis cluster diagrams offer a graphical resource or node representation to show similarities and differences. For convenience, the sources or nodes in a cluster analysis diagram are similar and do not differ. In this Cluster Analysis it can be measured about the correlation (Pearson

Coefficient when viewed from the correlation between the Pearson Correlation Coefficient). Cluster analysis in NVivo is carried out to explore the correlation of the contents of one text with another. The high and low Pearson correlation values displayed by NVivo illustrate the close relationship between the contents of one text and the contents of another text.

Fig. 17: Source triangulation

Word Cloud or also known as Tag Cloud is a data visualization method by showing how often a word appears

in the data represented by the size of the writing on the word cloud.

Fig. 18: Safety Guidelines Questions

Based on the results of the analysis, there are several words that often appear, namely work, accidents, employees, manuals, guidelines, safety. This can describe the focus of the study on the discussion of this research.

C. Safety Behavior Conditions for Occupational Safety and Health in the Bonded and Logistic Services Division of PT. GMFAeroasia Tbk?

Safety Behavior is a system that companies use to change unsafe behavior and attitudes of employees. Saodah (2019:28), Safety behavior educates employees to look for the root causes of accident-prone behavior. This makes employees aware of the behavioral tendencies that lead to a high risk of work accidents.

The condition of safety behavior in the Bonded and Logistic Services divisions is going well. This is proven by the results of the analysis test using the Nvivo application, where each research variable obtains an interrelated relationship from the word cloud.

D. Factors and Barriers to the Implementation of Safety Behavior on Occupational Health and Safety

From the answers of the informants regarding the benefits and effectiveness of the regulatory guidelines in this study, the researchers concluded that the HSE Manual regulatory guidelines were very useful and effective for reducing the number of work accidents in the Bonded and

Logistic Services divisions. The HSE Manual guideline contains regulations, the use of PPE, safety culture, and many other things regarding OHS in general or is broken down again according to the needs of the unit/division and their respective jobs, but there are still many employees who have not implemented these rule guidelines in their daily work properly and correctly, thus making the benefits and effectiveness of these rule guidelines uneven and the cause of work accidents still occurring in the Bonded and Logistic Services divisions.

E. Advice on the Concept of Correct Implementation of Safety Behavior for Occupational Safety and Health in the Bonded and Logistic Services Division of PT. GMFAeroasia Tbk

PT. GMFAeroasia Tbk, currently has regulatory guidelines related to the Occupational Health and Safety of its employees, where these rules are made on the basis of references to general rules relating to Occupational Health and Safety namely ISO 45001:2018, SMK 3 PP NO. 50/2012 and the international standard ISO 14001. Where the concept of HSE is generally divided into:

- Planning
- Realization
- Action
- Management Review

Fig. 19: OHS Guidelines Concepts

Meanwhile, the concept of regulatory guidelines related to occupational health and safety and related to safety behavior is divided into:

- Assessment of hazard risks and environmental aspects
- Compliance obligations

- Other issues and requirements
- Opportunity to deal with
- Mitigation
- The desired result

Fig. 20: K3 Rule Guidelines Concept at PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk

In general, the picture above is the basic concept of the rule guidelines regarding Occupational Health and Safety at PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk, but for its implementation it is adjusted to the conditions and needs of each division, from the results of research by researchers and the results of analysis of interview data with informants, researchers want to provide suggestions and additional points to the HSE Manual rule guidelines, especially for the Bonded and Logistic Services divisions. Suggestions and additional points are contained in several sections, including:

Hazard-Risk Assessment & Environment Aspect, The researcher wants to provide additional derivatives and elaborations and explanations regarding the hazard risk assessment and environmental aspects. The additional points referred to are as follows:

- Conduct routine health checks (MCU) for employees
- Checking work tools/tools in the work area
- Check the availability of hazard symbols in the work area

➤ *Compliance Obligations*

The researcher wants to provide additional derivatives and elaborations and explanations regarding obligations and compliance. The additional points referred to are as follows:

- Provide rewards to employees who implement safety behavior in accordance with the HSE Manual guidelines
- Provide punishment or warning to employees who do not implement safety behavior in accordance with the guidelines. In addition, changes to the reward or compensation structure can also be made to increase the motivation of employees to behave in safety according to regulatory guidelines (Sripada, 2020).

➤ *Opportunities to be Addressed and Mitigation*

Researchers want to provide additional derivatives and elaborations and explanations regarding opportunities to be addressed and mitigation. The additional points referred to are as follows:

- Provision of a place for employees to report to the authorized unit if they see colleagues who do not work according to the guidelines
- Provision of first aid kits in the work area of the Bonded Logistic Services division
- Provision of posters regarding reporting and mitigation guidelines in the event of a work accident

➤ *Desired results and prevention of work accidents*

The researcher wants to provide additional derivatives and elaborations and explanations regarding the desired results and prevention of work accidents. The additional points referred to are as follows:

- Carry out training activities for all employees regarding safety behavior as well as occupational health and safety
- Collaborating with outsiders/externals who can periodically share seasons regarding safety behavior.
- Holding a competition related to safety, where each employee can take part in the competition and the winner gets a reward so as to create a greater sense of concern for safety and rule guidelines.

The following begins with suggestions and additional points from researchers regarding manual HSE rule guidelines regarding safety behavior and occupational health and safety in the Bonded and Logistic Service division of PT GMF. Aeroasia Tbk:

Fig. 21: Chart of Suggestions and Additional Points from Researchers

Researchers provide suggestions and additional points to the existing model of occupational health and safety in hazard risk assessment, compliance obligations and other problems and needs. Where at these three points the researcher provides additional additional points to become derivatives so that the occupational health and safety chart in the Bonded Logistic Services division provides suggestions for implementing safety behavior towards occupational health and safety so that it is better in the future.

Where at the hazard risk assessment point consists of checking health conditions (medical checkups) routinely as well as checking work tools or tools that must be carried out also regularly, the aim is for employees to be more concerned about their safety behavior in carrying out and paying attention to each other's personal health and work tools used daily. Furthermore, the compliance obligation consists of giving rewards to employees who implement safety behavior correctly according to the guidelines and providing punishment for employees who do not implement safety behavior correctly according to existing regulatory guidelines. The goal is also the same as the first point so that employees are more concerned about their safety behavior.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on research that has been conducted regarding the implementation of safety behavior on occupational health and safety, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Conditions for implementing safety behavior on occupational health and safety at PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk especially the Bonded and Logistic Services division is guided by a guideline, the rule is called "HSE Manual" where the HSE Manual generally adheres to ISO 14000:1, OSH, and K3 management system (SMK3).

The HSE Manual was signed by the chairman of P2K3 where GMF itself is the director of Human Capital and General Affair. The HSE Manual itself has also been published and informed to all employees of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk especially the Bonded and Logistic Service division through various means including via email from the administrator regarding the latest updates regarding the "HSE Manual" rule guidelines, besides that it was also socialized that the HSE Manual can be accessed on the company's internal website, namely "GMF Sharepoint". Then for the socialization of the contents of the HSE Manual it is also published and socialized in accordance with the field of work or the division is socialized through people who are extensions of the management in each agency. HSE Manual rule guidelines, very useful and effective in reducing the number of work accidents in the Bonded and Logistic Services divisions.

- The factors of implementing safety behavior in accordance with the regulatory guidelines provide benefits and effectiveness in reducing the number of work accidents, these factors are the awareness factor, the work deadline factor, the understanding and knowledge factor. Where everything is contained in the guidelines for the HSE Manual rules listed regarding rules, use of PPE, safety culture, and many other matters regarding OHS in general or broken down again according to the needs of the units/divisions and their respective jobs, but there are still many employees who have not implemented these rule guidelines in their daily work properly and correctly, thus making the benefits and effectiveness of these rule guidelines uneven and the cause of work accidents still occurring in the Bonded and Logistic Services divisions.

- Obstacles encountered in the implementation of safety behavior towards occupational health and safety include working in a hurry because of pursuing the TAT which must be achieved immediately, not yet understanding the safety behavior guidelines properly, so as said by one informant who has a position as a Bonded Zone Analyst, obstacles in implementing safety behavior that are in accordance with the guidelines are also caused by work deadlines so employees often forget safety and safety regulations as well as Turnover and work time deadlines must be completed immediately, each employee who still does not care about himself or the condition of his co-workers, in addition to other factors the cause is tools and equipment that are still ineffective, because sometimes there are tools that are overdue causing work accidents, because sometimes the employee already knows that the tools/tools are overdue and not suitable for use, but because of work needs they are still used to work even though this is risky and can cause work accidents. In addition, the deadline/work TAT factor must be reached immediately which causes employees to be negligent in carrying out safety behavior towards themselves in their daily work.
- From the guidelines on safety behavior and Occupational Health and Safety, there are several additional points that can be added to the HSE manual so that in the future it will become an even better concept of regulatory guidelines including holding competitions related to safety, collaborating with outsiders/externals to share seasons on safety and K3, holding inspections/visit to divisions in PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk, one of which is the Bonded and Logistic Services division, to find out firsthand how the existing regulatory guidelines are realized. Carry out routine checks on tools as well as symbols and hazard logos in the work area, Give and carry out routine Medical Check-ups to employees within a certain period of time, provide a platform for employees to report to the authorized unit if they see co-workers not working according to the guidelines, some of these points can be added and become additional points to the pre-existing HSE Manual rule guidelines.

VI. MANAGERIAL ADVICE

Based on the results of research related to the implementation of safety behavior on occupational health and safety, the authors can provide the following suggestions: For the management and HSE division of PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk, suggestions and input from researchers related to regulatory guidelines regarding the implementation of safety behavior and occupational health and safety are:

Holding a competition related to safety, where each employee or agency can take part in the competition and those who win will receive a reward, thereby making a sense of concern for safety and guidelines for rules even greater.

Then the second is related to awareness of the implementation of safety behavior, the researcher suggests, collaboration can be carried out with external parties who can periodically share seasons regarding safety behavior.

This external party can be internal, such as a unit facility, or from an external party/HSE vendor, such as from an HSE vendor, for example, a 3M vendor. Where this will be something new and interesting to see and automatically people who see and participate in these activities indirectly enter into the minds of each individual and carry it out in their daily work. Conduct inspections / visits to divisions in PT. GMF Aeroasia Tbk, one of which is the Bonded and Logistic Services division, to find out firsthand how the existing regulatory guidelines are realized.

Carry out routine checks on tools and symbols and logos for danger signs in the work area including the work area of the Bonded and Logistic Services divisions to ensure that the existing tools are not overdue or suitable for use and to ensure that the symbols and danger signs in the work area are available.

Providing and carrying out routine Medical Check-up activities for employees within a certain period of time, considering the work environment which is side by side with heavy equipment and material parts, the worry is that there are employees who experience disturbances caused by this, such as breathing or other things that were not realized beforehand but with the suggestion that the MCU can become known to the employee and be more aware of his health.

Then finally, provide a platform for employees to report to the authorized unit if they see co-workers who do not work according to the guidelines and provide punishment or sanctions for employees who do not behave safety in working according to the regulatory guidelines to give a deterrent effect.

VII. FOR BONDED AND MATERIAL LOGISTIC SERVICES EMPLOYEES

Do not work too hard if you are not in good condition excellent even though being chased by deadlines and work TAT.

Can report to each other and remind colleagues if they see and find co-workers who do not behave safety according to the rules guidelines.

Do not take lightly the use of personal protective equipment when working that is heavy or light. Routinely check work tools and hazard symbols in the work area for self-protection.

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